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**Influence of the General Overseers'
Leadership Styles on Mission Strategies
and Infrastructural Development of the
Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria 2010-
2019**

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Abstract

Studies on leadership have become a prominent scholarly and professional pursuit in an ever-changing, highly complex, and multi-dimensional globalized world. Despite the significant body of literature on leadership, its influence and different styles continues to remain to attract attention in academic research. Therefore, this study investigated on the influence of the leadership styles of the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church in Nigeria on mission strategies and infrastructural development of the Church between 2010 and 2019. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The sample involve 172 respondents who were randomly selected among the leaders in the church. Self-designed, segmented, validated instruments were used to collect data for this study: (a). Leadership Styles Adoption Questionnaire (LSAQ); (b). Mission Strategies Adoption Questionnaire (MiSAQ); (c).

Infrastructural Development Adoption Questionnaire (IDAQ); and (d). Interview Guide for Organization Leaders (IGOL). Descriptive statistics was used for data analysis. The finding revealed that: the predominant leadership style adopted by General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999 and 2009 were democratic and partly autocratic leadership styles because these leadership styles are the ones having many items above the weighted mean (of $\bar{x} = 2.47$). Similarly, the findings indicated that General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria leadership styles of between 1999 and 2009 are impactful on medical services, treatment and provision of drugs etc. The study concludes that: the missionaries as leaders in the Church will have to develop leadership strategies that will enhance not only infrastructural facilities but also numerical and spiritual growth. The study recommends that: The leaders in the Church should be eclectic in their leadership style approaches as one leadership style cannot always suitable for situations in the Church, a mixture of democratic and autocratic leadership style will work perfectly in Church administration.

Keywords: Leadership-style, Mission-strategies, Infrastructural-development, Church-development

Introduction

Organizational leadership exhibits diverse styles with respect to what is expected of a leader to meet organizational goals. Also, leaders in different organizations will arrive with different styles with which to run the organization placed in his/her care, but what remains constant is that the already laid down styles serve as their pathways to achieving organizational desired goals. Church organisations, such as Foursquare Gospel Church, also place high demand in quality leadership. This is because, the Church started in Nigeria in October 1955 through the endeavours of a missionary couple: Rev. and Mrs. Harold Curtis from USA. The registered headquarters in Nigeria is at 62/66 Akinwunmi Street Yaba, Lagos State. The Foursquare Gospel Church in Nigeria currently has about 4032 churches spread over 154 districts and 824 zones. The founding fathers of The Foursquare Gospel Church in Nigeria were Rev. Odunaike Samuel Olusegun, Rev. Boyejo James Abayomi and Rev. Friday Chinyere Osuwa. The church is headed by the General Overseer and Senior Pastor. He is assisted by other ministers. The Foursquare Church in Nigeria has reached out to neighbouring countries and had established churches in the Republic of Benin, Ghana, Gambia, Liberia, Cote de voire and Central African Republic. Most of these churches in the west coast have been nationalized.

The expected leadership styles and expectations in The Foursquare Gospel Church (FGC) are embedded in the church policies, centred around the following: Church Growth Policy, Financial Policy, Membership Policy, Church Arms and Ministries Policy, Personnel Policy of the Church. Hence, the extent to which the church's policies are followed through is mostly dependent on the appointed leader. Therefore, the assertion which suggests that, leadership is key to good performance since it coordinates both utilization of human and other resources in the organization is right (NawoseIng'ollan & Roussel, 2020). Understanding the concept of leadership requires defining leadership itself, although, unambiguously it is not an easy task to define, as there is no agreed definition available in the literature Daniëls, Hondeghem & Dochy, 2019). There are numerous postulations and perceptions on leadership and most of them stipulate the concept in different ways, the assumption widely shared by authors is that leadership is a process of influencing in which an individual exerts intentional influence over others to structure activities and relationships in a group or organization (Rajab, 2021). Leadership can also be said to be the ability to influence an organization and direct it to a common goal. Leadership is the ability to carry an important role in the organization, so that organizational goals can be achieved properly and directed (Aussel & Svensson, 2020).

The objective is articulated by the leader who looks to gaining the commitment of staff and stakeholders to the dream of a better future for an organization, its staff and stakeholders. Good leader motivates team mates to increase job performances and commitment within an organization, and also go beyond the job requirements thus increasing the organization's general performance and positioning it to achieving its set vision. Leadership can be premised on the following dimensions: One, leadership is a process of influence to structure and organize the processes in the organization two, leadership is related to organizational values and committing people to these values, and, three, vision is an essential feature of effective leadership (Cortellazzo, Bruni & Zampieri, 2019).

Another author evaluated the extent to which organizational leadership and organizational success influence teachers' levels of job motivation and organizational commitment. This research was conducted at a private high school in Rawamangun Village, which is in the Pulo Gadung Sub-district of East Jakarta. The author used a saturated sample technique, which means the author took a representative sample from the entire population (i.e. 115

people). The Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) approach was chosen for statistical analysis. The findings revealed that the effectiveness of leadership and the level of trust in the organization had a direct and beneficial influence on work motivation. The level of trust inside an organization, as well as the effectiveness of its leadership have a direct and positive impact on the level of commitment within that organization. Both effective leadership and work motivation have direct and beneficial effects on organizational trust and commitment, respectively. The effectiveness of leaders has a direct and beneficial impact on organizational trust. As a result of this research, it is expected that it will increase the level of self-assurance, work motivation, and commitment of teachers in school organizations by providing input for the school in determining policies, specifically in determining position requirements or the recruitment of school principals (Rajbhandari, 2020).

Infrastructure development is regarded as a critical factor in promoting economic growth and attracting foreign investors in order to achieve long-term production and productivity. Beyond growth, development includes improved living conditions and welfare, as well as structural transformation of the economy from one based on subsistence and agriculture to one based on manufacturing, from which the majority of the population derives a living. One way to categorize different types of infrastructure is to divide them into two categories: hard infrastructure and soft infrastructure Muchiri, Gamage & Samad (2022). Hard infrastructure refers to the physical networks necessary for the functioning of a modern industry: This includes roads, bridges, and railways. Soft infrastructure refers to all the institutions that maintain the economic, health, social, environmental, and cultural standards of a country. The soft infrastructure includes educational programs, official statistics, parks and recreational facilities, law enforcement agencies, and emergency services (Al Khajeh, 2018).

For the purpose of this study, the concept of infrastructural development shall imply and include:

- i. Church Growth Policy:* the vigorous pursuit of the three components of the Great Commission as exemplified by Jesus Christ is: Preaching, Teaching and Healing.
- ii. Church Financial Policy:* Church Financial policies refer to policies related to the regulation, supervision, and oversight of the financial and payment systems, including markets and institutions, with the view to promoting financial stability, market efficiency, and client-

asset and consumer protection. The financial responsibility of the church is to be a wise steward of the resources God has entrusted to this fellowship. Ultimately, the church is responsible to God in the stewardship of its funds.

Through the Church arms and ministry's policy, The Foursquare Gospel Church in Nigeria since her establishment in 1955, has grown and continues to grow in line with biblical promises. The obvious growth equally spread beyond the shores of Nigeria cannot but be connected to the active activities of various arms of the Church (Muchiri, Gamage & Samad, 2022).

Statement of the Problem

While the concept of leadership has been conceived by different people, in different spheres of life, and with different perspectives, the concept remains quite a controversial discussion seeing that it has been used in the attainment of goals and objectives: positive and negative, and have produced desired and less desired outcomes in all its usage. Although there has been substantial research completed and authenticated with regard to what are now considered mainstream styles of accepted leadership, such as democratic, transactional, and transformational leadership, however, there is very little research on influence of leadership styles on mission strategies and infrastructural development of The Foursquare Gospel Church in Nigeria. The present study contributes to the closure of this research. Therefore, this study investigated the influence of the General Overseer's leadership styles on mission strategies and infrastructural development of Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria 2010-2019.

Aims and Objectives

This study aims to investigate General Overseers' leadership styles on mission strategies and infrastructural development of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria 2010-2019. The specific objectives are to:

1. identify the leadership styles of The Foursquare Gospel Church Nigeria between 2010 - 2019.
2. assess the effect of the leadership styles of The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the church mission strategies between 2010 – 2019.
3. assess the effect of the leadership styles of The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the church's infrastructural development between 2010 – 2019.

Research Questions

1. What are the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseer of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 2010 and 2019?
2. What are the influences of leadership styles of the General Overseer of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the adoption of the Church between 2010 and 2019?
3. What is the influence of Leadership Styles of the General overseer of The Foursquare Gospel Church Nigeria on Infrastructural Development between 2010 and 2019?

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. This design affords the researcher the opportunity to gather data from a large sample within the study area through Church Leaders and Administrative Officers of the Organisation. The population of the study include member of the Board of Trustees, members of the Board of Directors of The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria estimated at sixteen as well as member of the National Executive Council (NEC) who serve as Regional Coordinators, Axis Coordinators, District Overseers, District Coordinators, Head of Reconciliation Committee, Patron of Foursquare and Weekend of Transfigure National Evangelist Provost of Life Theological Seminary, Director School of Mission, Council of Foursquare Men, National President and some Administrative Officers in National Office. The estimated population was 220 which include NEC members and some administrative Officers at the National Office.

Furthermore, this study adopted multistage sampling procedure. Firstly, purposive sampling technique was adopted in selecting the respondents who are leaders in the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria. A total of 172 respondents were selected. Furthermore, the study also adopted stratified sampling technique to select twelve (12) nominated Leaders that served as key informant who were interviewed. Majority of the key informants have served for at least 40 years with the Organisation. Details as presented in Table 1.

Again, the research instruments for this study were three (3) questionnaire and one interview guide. The instruments were self-developed and they were used to gather data for the study. The instruments are: Leadership Styles Adoption Questionnaire (LSAQ); Mission Strategies Adoption

Questionnaire (MiSAQ); Infrastructural Development Adoption Questionnaire (IDAQ) and Interview Guide for Organization Leaders (IGOL) and to ascertain the reliability of the questionnaire, a pilot study was conducted. The psychometric value of the questionnaire was tested using Cronbach Alpha.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Gender, Age, Marital Status and Highest Educational Qualification (N=172)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	153	89.0
Female	19	11.0
Age		
Below 25years	5	3.0
30-40years	7	4.0
40-45years	3	2.0
45-50years	18	11.0
50-60years	71	41.0
61years and Above	68	39.0
Marital Status		
Single	12	7.0
Married	156	91.0
Widow	2	1.0
Widower	2	1.0
Highest Educational Qualification		
Primary Six	10	6.0
WASC/SSCE	8	5.0
Sub-degree e.g ND, NCE Certificate	5	3.0
Degree/HND	56	32.0
Master Degree	57	33.0
D.Min/PhD	36	21.0

Source: Field Work, 2023

Result and Discussion of Finding

Research Question One: What are the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseer of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019?

Table 2: Leadership Styles Adopted by the General Overseers of The Foursquare Gospel Church Nigeria between 2010-2009 (N=172)

Items on Democratic Leadership Style	HA	%	A	%	NA	%	Mean	SD	
Consider the needs of the organisation in the execution of the vision	11 6	67%	53	31%	3	2%	1.34	0.51	
Created an enabling environment for teamwork	73	42%	84	49%	15	9%	1.66	0.63	
Acknowledged, appreciated and gave due credit to the support of the workers	74	43%	93	54%	5	3%	1.60	0.55	
Put the options of the people into consideration	57 6	33%	10 6	62%	9	5%	1.72	0.56	
Handled conflicts effectively without injustice	56	33%	84	49%	32	18 %	1.86	0.70	
Promoted a strong partnership between the leader and the led	63	36%	10 3	60%	6	4%	1.67	0.54	
Encouraged transparency in the leader-led relationship	75	44%	81	47%	16	9%	1.66	0.64	
Were accountable for decisions and actions	72	42%	86	50%	14	8%	1.66	0.62	
							1.66	0.62	
Weighted Mean									

Items on Autocratic Leadership Style								
Made irrevocable decisions even when it was disadvantageous to the members of the organization	34	20%	71	41%	67	39%	2.19	0.74
Prevented interpersonal relationship with the members of the organization	24	14%	49	29%	99	57%	2.44	0.73
Imposed their vision on the members in the organisation without consultation and proper consideration	20	12%	47	27%	105	61%	2.49	0.69
Prevented workers/members from expressing themselves through their rigidity	14	8%	48	28%	110	64%	2.56	0.64
Accepted no input from workers/members in the organisation	15	9%	36	21%	121	70%	2.62	0.64
Promoted a structure that encouraged monotony	19	11%	38	22%	115	67%	2.56	0.68
							2.47	0.68
Weighted Mean								

Items on Laissez-faire Leadership Style									
Provided little guidance to the members	15	9%	41	24%	11	67	2.59	0.65	
Expected people to solve their own problems	16	9%	63	37%	93	54	2.45	0.66	
Took responsibility for overall actions and decisions	50	29%	96	56%	26	15	1.86	0.65	
Gave members the ability to make decisions	42	25%	10	59%	28	16	1.92	0.64	
Took charge only when necessary	43	25%	69	40%	60	33	2.10	0.77	
Provided a creative environment that promoted variety	70	41%	78	45%	24	14	1.73	0.69	
							2.11	0.67	
Weighted Mean									

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork 2023.

Table 2 reveals that six out of eight items used to measure the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019 are having mean (\bar{x}) above the weighted mean taken as the benchmark (1.66). For instance, on the item which stated that: Created an enabling environment for teamwork ($\bar{x} = 1.66$), put the options of the people into consideration ($\bar{x} = 1.72$), handled conflicts effectively without injustice ($\bar{x} = 1.86$), promoted a strong partnership between the leader and the led ($\bar{x} = 1.67$), encouraged transparency in the leader-led relationship ($\bar{x} = 1.66$) and were accountable for decisions and actions ($\bar{x} = 1.66$).

However, items (1 and 3 (\bar{x}) means respectively) are below the set benchmark. This result indicates that General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria used democratic leadership style between 1999-

2009 since the number of items that are having mean above the bench mark is greater than those who have mean below.

Table 2 shows the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseer of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 2010 and 2019. To answer Research Question One, the weighted mean (2.47) was determined for the section on autocratic leadership style and taken as bench mark for the explanation of the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseer of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 2010 and 2019. The table reveals that four out of six items used to measure the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseer of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 2010 and 2019 are having mean (\bar{x}) above the weighted mean taken as the benchmark (2.47). For instance, on the item which stated that: Imposed their vision on the members in the organisation without consultation and proper consideration ($\bar{x} = 2.49$), prevented workers/members from expressing themselves through their rigidity ($\bar{x} = 2.56$), accepted no input from workers/members in the organisation ($\bar{x} = 2.62$), promoted a structure that encouraged monotony ($\bar{x} = 2.56$). However, items (1 and 2 (\bar{x}) means respectively) are below the set bench mark. This result indicates that General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria used autocratic leadership style between 2010-2009 since the number of items that are having mean above the bench mark is greater than those who have mean below.

Similarly, Table 2 shows the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 2010 and 2019. To answer research question one, the weighted mean (2.11) was determined for the section on laissez-faire leadership style and taken as bench mark for the explanation of the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria in 2010-2019. The table reveals that three out of six items used to measure the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019 are having mean (\bar{x}) above the weighted mean taken as the benchmark (2.11). For instance, on the item which stated that: Provided little guidance to the members ($\bar{x} = 2.59$), expected people to solve their own problems ($\bar{x} = 2.45$), took charge only when necessary ($\bar{x} = 2.10$). However, items (3, 4 and 5 (\bar{x}) means respectively) are below the set benchmark. This result indicates that General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria used laissez-faire leadership style between 1999-

2009 since the number of items that are having mean above the bench mark is equal to items who are having mean below.

Invariably, the finding on research question one reveals that the predominant leadership style adopted by General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2009 were democratic and partly autocratic leadership styles because these leadership styles are the ones having many items above the weighted mean (of $\bar{x} = 2.47$).

Research Question Two: What are the influences of leadership styles of the General Overseer of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the adoption of the Church between 2010 and 2019?

Table 3: Influence of Leadership Styles of the General Overseer of The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the Adoption of the Church between 2010 and 2019

Influence of Leadership Styles on the Mission Strategies	HA	%	A	%	NA	%	Mean	S
	N	%	N	%	N	%		D
Medical services, treatment and provision of drugs	44	26%	69	40%	59	34%	2.09	0.77
Food supplies and feeding during festive period	50	29%	75	44%	47	27%	1.98	0.75
Vocational development	32	19%	73	42%	67	39%	2.20	0.73
Establishment of Foursquare National Evangelists	60	35%	61	36%	51	29%	1.95	0.80
Establishment of television station	57	33%	45	26%	70	41%	2.08	0.86

Establishment of schools, colleges and university	89	52%	58	34%	25	14%	1.63	0.73
Establishment of hospitals, guest house and conference center	56	33%	77	45%	39	22%	1.90	0.74
Establishment of College of Theology	77	45%	60	35%	35	20%	1.76	0.77
Water supply	40	23%	96	56%	36	21%	1.98	0.67
Financial support scheme/interest-free loan scheme	33	19%	58	34%	81	47%	2.28	0.77
							1.98	0.76
Weighted Mean								

Source: Fieldwork 2023

To answer Research Question Three, the weighted mean (1.94) was determined and taken as bench mark for the explanation of (Influence of) the leadership styles of the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the mission strategies adoption of the Church in 2010-2019. Table 3 shows the Influence of the adopted leadership styles of the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the mission strategies adoption of the Church in 2010-2009.

The table further reveals that thirteen out of twenty items used to measure the (Influence of) the leadership styles of the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the mission strategies adoption of the Church between 1999-2019 are having mean (\bar{x}) same and above the weighted mean taken as the benchmark (1.94). For instance, on the item which stated that: Medical services, treatment and provision of drugs ($\bar{x} = 2.09$), food supplies and feeding during festive period ($\bar{x} = 1.98$), vocational development ($\bar{x} = 2.20$), establishment of foursquare national evangelists ($\bar{x} = 1.95$), establishment of television station ($\bar{x} = 2.08$), water supply ($\bar{x} = 1.98$), financial support scheme/interest-free loan scheme ($\bar{x} = 2.28$), distribution of bible and Christian materials/literature ($\bar{x} = 2.05$), grace power night ($\bar{x} = 2.00$), correctional home fellowship ($\bar{x} = 1.97$), educational

support services ($\bar{x} = 2.03$) and youth empowerment ($\bar{x} = 2.06$), However, items (6,7, 8, 16, 17, 18, 19 and 20 (\bar{x}) means respectively) are below the set bench mark.

Findings on Research Question Two indicated that General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria leadership styles of between 2010-2009 is impactful on medical services, treatment and provision of drugs, food supplies and feeding during festive period, vocational development, establishment of foursquare national evangelists, establishment of television station, water supply, financial support scheme/interest-free loan scheme, distribution of Bible and Christian materials/literature, grace power night, correctional home fellowship, educational support services and youth empowerment respectively.

Research Question Three: What is the influence of Leadership Styles of the General overseer of The Foursquare Gospel Church Nigeria on Infrastructural Development between 2010 and 2019?

Table 4: Leadership Styles of the General Overseer on Infrastructural Development between 2010-2009 (N=172)

Leadership Style on The Mission Strategies	HI	MI	NI	Mean	SD
Building of summary classroom	62 (36%)	65 (38%)	45 (26%)	1.90	0.79
Building of more churches	81 (47%)	75 (44%)	16 (9%)	1.62	0.65
Creation of more zones	79 (46%)	75 (44%)	18 (10%)	1.65	0.66
Creation of more district	77 (45%)	75 (44%)	20 (11%)	1.67	0.68
Upgrade of church building	58 (34%)	87 (51%)	27 (15%)	1.82	0.68
Establishment of Foursquare Barley Harvest Radio	86 (50%)	51 (30%)	35 (20%)	1.70	0.78
Building of primary and secondary schools	53 (31%)	80 (47%)	39 (22%)	1.92	0.73

Creation of more axis and regions	54 (31%)	60 (35%)	58 (34%)	2.02	0.81
Building of Foursquare Hospital	49 (29%)	55 (32%)	68 (39%)	2.11	0.82
Establishment of Conference center	77 (45%)	74 (43%)	21 (12%)	1.67	0.68
Development of Camp facilities	77 (45%)	71 (41%)	24 (14%)	1.69	0.70
Guest Houses	51 (30%)	73 (42%)	48 (28%)	1.98	0.76
Building of Mission schools	50 (29%)	89 (52%)	33 (19%)	1.90	0.69
Borehole Drilling	50 (29%)	94 (55%)	28 (16%)	1.87	0.66
Vocational Training Facilities	45 (26%)	92 (54%)	35 (20%)	1.94	0.68
				1.83	0.72

Weighted Mean

Source: Field work, 2023

Table 4 shows the level of infrastructural performance in The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 2010 and 2019. To answer research question on this variable, the weighted mean (1.83) was determined and taken as bench mark for the explanation of the level of infrastructural performance of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 2010 and 2019. The table reveals that eight out of fifteen items used to measure the level of infrastructural performance The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019 are having mean (\bar{x}) above the weighted mean taken as the benchmark (1.83). For instance, on the item which stated that: Building of summary classroom ($\bar{x} = 1.90$), Building of primary and secondary schools ($\bar{x} = 1.92$), Creation of more axis and regions ($\bar{x} = 2.02$), Building of Foursquare Hospital ($\bar{x} = 2.11$), Guest Houses ($\bar{x} = 1.98$), Building of Mission schools ($\bar{x} = 1.90$), Borehole Drilling ($\bar{x} = 1.87$) and Vocational Training Facilities ($\bar{x} = 1.94$). However, items (2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 10 and 11 (\bar{x}) means respectively) are below the set bench mark.

The findings on Research Question Three indicated that in The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria General Overseer's Leadership style/influence in

building of seminary classrooms, building of primary and secondary schools, creation of more axis and regions, building of foursquare hospital, guest houses, building of mission schools, borehole drilling and vocational training facilities receptively between 2010-2009.

Discussion of Findings

This study investigated influences of leadership styles the General Overseers on mission strategies and infrastructural development of the Foursquare Gospel Church in Nigeria. Findings on Research Question One revealed that the General Overseers in Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria predominantly employed democratic leadership style during the period examine in this study i.e. (2010-2019), even though some responses are indicative of partly adoption of autocratic and laissez-faire leadership style. This finding aligns with some authors' postulation that one leadership style cannot be suitable at all time for all the circumstances in an Organisation which Church founded. Therefore, the finding supports an author who postulated that the essence of leadership is that an individual's ability to influence others has an impact on changing the behaviour of others: behaviour changes to achieve a common goal (Nandasinghe, 2020). A leader has a set of qualities or characteristics with which he or she can influence others. The success of an organization depends on the quality of its leadership. Leadership is recognized as the key to successful leadership. Leadership impacts the behaviour and results of organizational performance.

The finding on Research Question Two is also in consonance with the assertion of an author who conducted a study that focused on leadership styles: transformational, transactional, autocratic, charismatic, bureaucratic, and democratic. The findings suggested that charismatic, bureaucratic, and transactional leadership styles have negative relationships with organizational performance. Transformational, autocratic, and democratic leadership styles on the other hand, had a positive relationship with organizational performance (Lewa, Lewa & Mutuku, 2018). The author discovered that transformational, autocratic, and democratic leadership styles were found to have a positive influence on organizational performance, whereas the transactional, charismatic, and bureaucratic leadership styles were found to have a negative impact on organizational performance. The study further revealed that organizational performance is associated with the leadership style and they have both a

positive and a negative impact on the performance. It is important for a leadership style to offer opportunities to employees, offer a sense of belonging along with allowing them to participate in the decision-making. The finding on Research Question Three agrees with Al Khajeh (2018) who determined which of the four traditional leadership styles was most common. The first three types of leadership style are autocratic, democratic, and laissez-faire. The theory of multi-flex leadership style blends is used in this study to analyse the dominant leadership styles within these four traditional leadership styles. Among the different leadership philosophies, categories associated to multi-flex leadership styles were matched to a conceptual theoretical structure and infrastructural development. This strategy allowed for a more thorough examination of the four traditional leadership styles. The findings of this study demonstrate how the six multi-flex leadership styles interact with more traditional leadership philosophies to determine level of infrastructural development in the sampled organisation.

Conclusion

This study discussed the Influence of Leadership Styles of General Overseers of Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on Mission Strategies and Infrastructural Development 2010-2019. The findings from this study shown that significant relationship between leadership styles of the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church and Church Infrastructural Developments. The implication of the findings is that the missionaries as leaders in the Church will have to develop leadership strategies that will enhance not only infrastructural facilities but also numerical and spiritual growth.

Recommendations

The findings summarized above have far-reaching implications for church leaders, members, evangelists, body of Christ and Church Board of Trustee who are the major stakeholders in the Church administration. Therefore, the following recommendations were made:

1. The leaders in the Church should be eclectic in their leadership style approaches as one leadership style cannot always suitable for situations in the Church, a mixture of democratic and autocratic leadership style will work perfectly in Church administration.

2. Leaders in the Church should be prudent in the selection of the leadership style that will engender infrastructural development because this study established the fact that leadership style relates with infrastructural development.

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